

juncea L., in a randomized block design with three replications.

The second rice crop (CO 43) Nov 1985-Feb 1986 was grown in a split-plot design, with no additional fertilizer and with the recommended 26 kg P/ha as

superphosphate and as rock phosphate in combination with incorporated stubble cut 10 cm and 25 cm high.

Green gram *Vigna radiata* L. Wilczek was grown Feb-May 1986 without fertilizer. A fourth crop rice Jun-Sep

1986 was grown with the treatments given the first crop rice, substituting green gram haulm for sunn hemp.

The Mussoorie rock phosphate used was analyzed as 1.48% citrate soluble P_2O_5 , and 20% total P_2O_5 . Soil was Typic Haplustalf with pH 8.1, 0.6% organic C, CEC 27 meq/100 g, and 16 kg available P/ha. Inorganic N and K fertilizers were applied at recommended levels.

In the first crop rice, green manure plus superphosphate gave higher yields (see table). In the second crop rice, yields were higher where the first crop had been given superphosphate with or without green manure and rock phosphate with green manure.

In the second crop rice, yield was higher with superphosphate and long stubble incorporation. Residual effects of treatments given the first rice crop on the green gram crop of treatments given the first rice crop were not significant.

Superphosphate with long or short stubble incorporation in the second crop improved green gram yield.

Yield of the fourth crop rice was significantly improved by green gram haulm incorporation; P application had no significant effect. ■

Yields of rice-based cropping system under integrated P management Coimbatore, India, 1985-86.

First crop rice Jun-Oct 1985		Second crop rice Nov 1985-Feb 1986		Third crop green gram Feb-May 1986		Fourth crop rice Jun-Sep 1986	
Treatment ^a	Grain yield (t/ha)	Treatment ^a	Grain yield (t/ha)	Treatment ^a	Grain yield (kg/ha)	Treatment ^a	Grain yield (t/ha)
G ₀	4.4	G ₀ P ₀	4.4	G ₀ P ₀	393	G ₀	4.3
G ₁	5.2	G ₀ P _s	5.3	G ₀ P _s	400	G ₁	5.1
LSD (0.05)	0.4	G ₀ P _r	4.6	G ₀ P _r	456	LSD (0.05)	0.5
		G ₁ P ₀	4.9	G ₁ P ₀	443		
P ₀	4.4	G ₁ P _s	5.6	G ₁ P _s	499	P ₀	4.5
P ₅	5.3	G ₁ P _r	5.0	G ₁ P _r	451	P _s	4.9
P ₁	4.6	LSD (0.05)	0.6	LSD (0.05)	ns	P _r	4.6
LSD (0.05)	0.5					LSD (0.05)	ns
		S ₀ P ₀	4.7	S ₀ P ₀	390		
		S ₀ P _s	5.0	S ₀ P _s	500		
		S ₀ P _r	4.9	S ₀ P _r	412		
		S ₁ P ₀	4.7	S ₁ P ₀	405		
		S ₁ P _s	5.4	S ₁ P _s	515		
		S ₁ P _r	5.1	S ₁ P _r	421		
		LSD (0.05)	0.3	LSD (0.05)	70		

^aG₀ = no green manure, G₁ = green manure; P₀ = no phosphate, P_s = superphosphate, P_r = Rock phosphate; S₀ = 10-cm stubble incorporated, S₁ = 25-cm stubble incorporated.

Nitrogen loss by ammonia volatilization from urea and ammonium chloride in flooded soil

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Rapid hydrolysis of urea to ammonium carbonate can cause high concentrations of NH_4^+ -N and high floodwater pH, leading to high ammonia volatilization. In contrast, the low pH of ammonium chloride may help minimize ammonia volatilization from soils. We measured NH_3 volatilization from urea and ammonium chloride using the forced-draft chamber technique in the laboratory.

We used a set of 10-liter pots with 7 kg air-dried soil (pH 8.05, 0.32% organic C, 0.06% total N, CEC 9.5 meq/100 g). The soil was flooded, puddled, and allowed to preincubate with 1 cm

standing water for 1 wk. Pots were fertilized with 26 mg P and 50 mg K/kg applied as single superphosphate and muriate of potash.

Treatments were urea, urea + N-(n-butyl) thiophosphoric triamide (NBT) (2% wt/wt), ammonium chloride, and no N. N was applied at 200 kg/ha.

Soil was reflooded and evaporation losses replenished daily to maintain 5 cm standing water. Water temperatures ranged from 22.5 to 27.5°C.

Two pots/treatment were fitted with chambers continuously flushed with NH_3 -free compressed air. NH_3 was collected at intervals using a manifold and estimated by absorbing in 2% boric acid-mixed indicator solution. Floodwater was analyzed for ammoniacal N and pH.

N loss by ammonia volatilization was markedly affected by source of fertilizer (Fig. 1). In ammonium chloride-treated soil, ammonia volatilization was almost uniform up to 12 d after fertilizer applica-

1. Effect of urea, urea + NBT, and ammonium chloride on cumulative loss of ammonia from flooded sandy loam soil, Ludhiana, India.

tion. With urea alone, ammonia volatilization loss appeared within 5 d and rate increased up to 12 d, then decreased. With NBT-treated urea, ammonia volatilization was low up to 7 d, then increased consid-

erably up to 20 d. At 27 d, cumulative NH_3 volatilization was 4.8% of added ammonium chloride, 8.9% of urea +NBT, and 9.6% of urea.

NH_3 volatilization of ammonium chloride was half that of urea. Treating urea with NBT delayed ammonia volatilization about 7 d, but was ineffective thereafter.

The significant difference in ammonia volatilization loss between urea and ammonium chloride fertilizer was basically due to markedly lower floodwater pH in the ammonium chloride-treated soil (Fig. 2). Floodwater ammoniacal-N concentration was quite high in ammonium-chloride treated soil, indicating that ammonia gas concentration, not ammoniacal-N concentration, caused higher NH_3 volatilization loss in urea-treated soil. ■

2. Effect of urea and ammonium chloride on floodwater pH and NH_4^+ -N concentration, Ludhiana, India.

Crop management

Abscisic acid analog inhibits rice leafrolling caused by chilling

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One of the first symptoms of chilling injury to rice is leafrolling. This has been demonstrated to be due to water loss, and is correlated with leaf water potential.

We studied the effect of a new abscisic acid analog on leafrolling in response to chilling. Twelve-day-old seedlings of Samgangbyeon and 24-d-old seedlings of IR36 were sprayed with 10^{-4} and 10^{-3} , mol LAB 173711 per liter (abscisic acid analog developed by BASF, FRG) and a combination of LAB 173711 and tetcyclacis (a plant growth retardant). After 24 h, seedlings were transferred to a water tank for 3 d: Samgangbyeon seedlings for a root temperature of 11 °C for 7 d and IR36 for a root temperature of 5 °C. All seedlings were transferred to 29 °C for recovery.

Completely rolled leaves were counted and percent leafrolling calculated.

Leafrolling in Samgangbyeon and IR36 seedlings treated with abscisic acid analogs and chilled.

In Samgangbyeon seedlings submerged at 11 °C, treatment reduced leafrolling (see figure). It was only $\pm 2\%$ with LAB 173711 + tetcyclacis, about 30% with LAB 173711 alone, and 95% with no treatment. In IR36 seedlings submerged at 5 °C, leafrolling was minimized with ABA and LAB 173711 (only 4-10% rolling, compared with about 60% with no treatment). At 29 °C, rolled IR36 leaves reached 100% in the control and less than 40% in ABA- and LAB 173711-treated plants.

The effect may be due to the anti-transpirant activity of the analog: preventing water loss by transpiration and maintaining high internal water status for the plant system minimize or reduce leafrolling and, in turn, chilling injury. ■

Effect of nursery seeding density and seedlings/hill on late transplanted rice

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Although nursery seeding rates of 30, 40, and 50 kg/ha are recommended for small-medium-, and large-grain rices, respectively, farmers in many areas tend to sow at 60-80 kg/ha for weed control. In many rainfed rice areas, late rains also mean aged seedlings are transplanted.

We studied the effect of nursery seeding density and seedlings/hill on yields of late planted wet season rice. The trial was laid out in split-plot design with three replications. Soil was sandy loam (Typic Ustochrept) with pH 7.5 (1:2) and 0.58% organic C. Seedlings 40-45 d old were transplanted at 20- × 15-cm spacing the last week of Jul.

Nursery seeding density and seedlings/hill did not affect yield. ■

Effect of nursery management on performance of inland valley swamp rice in Sierra Leone

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We evaluated in 1988 wet season crop performance in an inland valley swamp of rice seedlings raised in the uplands. The soil was clay (Typic Tropaquept), with pH (water 1:1) 3.9, 6 kg Olsen's P/ha, 79 kg Olsen's K/ha, 3.2% organic C, and 0.12% total N.

ROK11 (130 d), ROK5 (145 d), and ROK10 (178 d) were planted at two seeding rates with two methods of sowing, and at two levels of fertilizer (see table). The experiment was laid out in a randomized complete block design with three replications. The nursery was systematically laid out in an upland site. Seedling vigor and vigor index (seedling length [including root] × dry weight) were evaluated 27 d after seeding.

Seedlings were transplanted at two seedlings/hill, at 0.15- × 0.2-m spacing.